

THE PROVISION OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING AMONG SENIOR HIGH STUDENTS OF THE MADINA-ADENTAN MUNICIPALITY

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Abstract: This study therefore seeks to explore the role of guidance and counselling in the life of students, in the Madina-Adenta Municipality in the Greater Accra Region of Ghana. It is specifically seeks to assess the extent to which senior high schools in the Madina-Adenta Municipality have adopted guidance and counselling and evaluate the effect of guidance and counselling services on the students in the Madina-Adenta Municipality. The study used purposive sampling to select both private and a government school, who have form 3 students. A simply random sampling is employed in getting the students to responses to the survey questions. It became clear from the result that females sought counselling more than the male students. The students do not usually seek counselling from their teachers or dedicated staff but relied more on their peers. These negative forces of peer pressure drive them into most of the undisciplined behaviours that largely can affect their academic performance and gradually wade away their desire for a good future career. It is recommended that students are trained as peer counselling. More peer counselling programmes in the SHS schools.

Keywords: Counselling, Guidance, Evaluate, Dedicated, Peer.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is often an overlooked fact that basic and Senior High School Guidance and Counselling can significantly influence student achievement, retention and behavior in schools. Research conducted by Borders and Drury (1992) found that school counselling interventions have a substantial impact on student's educational and personal development. Studies of a five-year dropout prevention by Kaufman, Klein and Frase (1999) showed that counselling services were one of the key elements encouraging pupils and students to stay in school. Afande (2015) points to the fact that many other studies lead to similar relationships between effective school counselling programs and student success. School guidance and counselling programs have therefore been introduced to assist students to overcome and adjust to a host of social and emotional challenges they experience at home and at school.

According to Gatua (2014), virtually all countries have established channels to intensify and improve guidance and counselling services in their respective learning institutions in an attempt to address tenets of students' behaviours. The history of guidance and counselling around the world varies greatly based on how different countries and local communities have chosen to provide personal, academic, social and emotional adjustment among the senior high school students (Weiten, 2007). Kaminer (2004) contends that in the United States, the school counselling profession began as a vocational guidance movement at the beginning of the 20th century when a systematic school guidance program was

developed and provided for the consumption by the schools. The movement emphasized personal issues, social and emotional adjustments in order to develop and promote students' character and avoid behavioural problems. In Japan, the goal of high school guidance and counselling services is to help every student develop abilities of self-understanding, decision making, life planning studies on the modification of behaviour among students and action taking to be able to adjust to social and emotional problems (Loescher, 2007)

Here in Ghana, the purpose and effect of educational counselling are hardly felt. This seems to be the case in many schools, both basic and high schools, public and private schools, not having counsellors in the schools for effective counselling service. In cases where there are counsellors, about 99% of them are estimated to be non-professionals (Brako-Powers, 2016). Before any attempts were made to establish formalized Guidance in Ghana in the 1960s, there existed forms of guidance through voluntary and non-formalized means. This took place in the form of pastoral care by significant persons in the school, church, home, and community. According to Dankwa (1981), guidance during this era was voluntary and was administered in the school system (second cycle institutions) especially in the boarding schools by heads prefects and house masters and mistresses.

According to (Kuhl, 1994), guidance and counselling programs has generally yielded positive outcome as it enhanced student learning and has been recommended as the preferred model of guidance service delivery to schools Gysbers and Blair, 1999; Sink and MacDonald, (1998). Lapan et al. (1997), reported that schools with more fully implemented guidance programs had students who were more likely to report that they had earned higher grades, were better prepared for their future, had more career and college information available to them, and also the fact that their school had a more positive climate.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The absence of guidance and counselling services to students Senior High Schools usually leave students uninformed and make them become victims of negative peer pressure. These negative forces of peer pressure drive them into undisciplined behaviour that largely affect their academic performance and gradually take away their desire for a good future career.

In the view of Weissberg & Myrskis (2007), the need for guidance and counselling services in all Senior High Schools cannot be overstated due to increasingly complexities of modern life that have placed heavy demands and responsibilities on Senior High Schools students. These students are faced with numerous personal, academic, social and emotional needs and problems when unattended could lead to host patterns of undesirable behaviours (Weiten, 2007).

More seriously, the Ghanaian educational system is being faced with several issues that call for concern. Some of these issues include drug abuse, addictions, irresponsible sexual behaviour, examination malpractice and other forms of violence. These cases of indiscipline keep rising, especially among the senior high students. Studies by Carey and Harrington (2010) have shown that young people at the senior high school levels usually have reached a stage in their lives where they are leaving their childhood and growing into adulthood, as a result potentially face conflict of personality, which promotes some of these behaviours

It is important therefore to ascertain, in view of all these societal challenges, the role guidance and counselling would play in making a difference in the lives of these Senior High School Students, on the personal and academic levels and shape their perspectives for a good future career.

3. PURPOSE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study was to establish the impact of guidance and counselling on Senior High School Students in the Madina-Adentan Municipality in the Greater Accra Region. This was achieved by assessing the extent to which senior high schools in the Madina-Adentan Municipality have adopted guidance and counselling. And then evaluate the effect of guidance and counselling services among students in the Municipality.

The research will help teachers and school administrators gain understanding of the importance of guidance and counselling in schools, aimed at enhancing discipline and subsequently affect the academic performance of students and their social life in general. Secondly, the Government, the Ministry of Education and Ghana Education Service as policy makers and other policy makers will appreciate the gaps existing in guidance and counselling related issues in schools. It would provide the basis for making informed decisions such as possible inclusion of guidance and counselling to the curriculum that train teachers and the creation of the means to access such services.

4. LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1 The concept of Guidance and Counselling

Guidance and Counseling is an interactive relationship that takes place between the Counselor and that client (in this case between you the counselor and the student), Gatua (2014). Meanwhile, the terms guidance and counselling have been loosely or interchangeably used. According to Chibber (1999), guidance is a term which is broader than counseling and it includes counseling as one of its services. In advancing this position, Butter (2009), makes a logical separation of the counseling process into two phases. The phases are the adjustive and the distributive phase. In the adjustive phase, the emphasis is on social, personal and emotional problems of the individual, in the distributive phase the focus is upon educational, vocational and occupational problems. The distributive phase can be most aptly described as guidance while the adjustive phase can be considered as the description of counselling.

4.2 Types of Counselling

There are two major types of Counselling, namely: individual counselling and group counselling. *Individual Counselling* is referred to as one-to-one counselling. It occurs between the professionally trained Counsellor (Therapist) and his client (Counselee). The goal of this is to help the client to understand himself, clarify and direct his thought, in order to make a worthwhile decision. Through this, clients' problems are alleviated. Frumboltz and Thoreson (1967) as cited in Ojo (2005) remarked that it is mainly to bring about change in the client either by altering maladaptive behavior, learning the decision-making process or preventing problems.

Group Counselling is a counselling session that takes place between the professionally trained counsellor and a group of people. Number of this group should not be more than seven, or at least ten, in order to have a cohesive group and an effective well controlled counselling session. Members of the groups are clients/counselees whose tasks or problems that are meant for resolution are similar. During group counselling, a free atmosphere is allowed and freedom of speech is encouraged. The counselees are free to express themselves individually as counselling progresses so that problems to be resolved would be open for all to consider and benefit from. All counselees express their feelings and the counselor during group counselling is to help remove the marks covering the problem. The counsellor helps open up the problem with the professional competence and knowledge possessed. The counsellor is not just a member of the group but responsible for giving directions on the affairs and situations.

4.3 Relationship in Counselling

Relationship has been recognized as one of the fundamental aspects of providing facilitation for the client's decision-making process. Sexton and Whiston (1994) conclude that of all the examined factors affecting the therapeutic process only the relationship has consistently contributed to success. Kolden et al (1994) suggest that the relationship serves the fundamental purpose of providing conditions for change and to provide the power by which change can be facilitated. Kiesler (1996) also suggests that the most important contextual environment in therapy is the relationship. The in-session relationship is identified as an important factor to provide conditions for a positive outcome but the definition of the relationship and the important components, in the relationship seems to be argumentative. Horvath and Greenberg (1989) argue that there are some major theoretical, technique specific, formulations whose purpose is to define and explore variables that are important for the relationship and the outcome of counselling.

4.4 Guidance and Counselling in Education

According to Nanda and Sharma (2002), the aim of education is to achieve the fullest possible realization of possibilities inherent in the individual. Education fosters all aspects of an individual's personality. Guidance and counselling are an integral part of education and helps in achieving the goals of education. This is quite essential for the development of individual which is the main objective of education. In this case guidance and counselling should be regarded as an integral part of education and not as a special, psychological or social service which is peripheral to educational purposes, (Nanda and Sharma, 2002). It is meant for all students not just for those who deviate from the norm in one direction or the other. Jones (1999), pointing out the relationship between guidance and counselling and education observes that all guidance is education but some aspects of education are not guidance. Their objectives are the same, that is, the development of the individual but methods used in education are by no means the same as those used in guidance and counselling.

4.5 The Assessment of Guidance and Counselling Services in Africa

In Africa, the concept of Guidance and Counselling although relatively new in educational systems, has been embraced by most governments (UNESCO, 2001). Although most African countries recognize the essential role of organized Guidance and Counselling Programmes, there are limited research studies conducted to assess the effectiveness of the programmed services being implemented to improve the students' decision-making processes that lead to improved future benefits (Biswalo, 1996; Folkman and Moskowitz, 2004). In Malawi, Maluwa (1998) in Chireshe, (2006) reveals that Career-Guidance and Counselling services help students to better understand their own interests, abilities and potentials; and how to develop them fully and subsequently make informed career choice decisions. With similar benefits in Kenya, Guidance and Counselling was formally introduced in institutions of learning in 1971 (Muture and Ndambuki, 2004). Guidance and Counselling in Tanzania is regarded a redundant and lacking trained personnel to provide effective services (Biswalo, 1996). Studies by Flisher, Zieger, Chalron, Leger and Robertson (2006) revealed that in South Africa there is a prevalence of risk taking adolescents attending secondary education.

Empirical Literature

Several studies found that guidance and counselling activities have a positive influence on students' academic achievement (Sink and Stroh, 2003). School counselling interventions have reported success for helping students reduce test anxiety (Cheek et al, 2002). School counsellors in collaborative efforts can implement both systemic and programmatic changes in schools and communities to prevent students from dropping out of school (Standard, R.P., 2003). Studies on high school attrition indicate that preventive counselling, occurring before students are in crisis, reduces the risk of these students dropping out later. According to Hayes et al (2002), counselling decreases classroom disturbances. Counselling services support teachers in the classroom and enable teachers to provide quality instruction designed to assist students in achieving high standards. Students in schools that provide counselling services indicated that their classes were less likely to be interrupted by other students, and that their peers behaved better in school (Mullis and Otwell, 1997).

In studies on the effects of a small group counselling approach for failing elementary school students, 83% of participating students showed improvement in grades (Boutwell and Myrick, 1992). School counselling programs have significant influence on discipline problems. Children who are experiencing family problems report being helped by school counsellors (Rose and Rose, 1992). School counsellors help connect the family as a whole to the educational process (Bemak and Cornely, 2002). School counsellors have proven effective in preventing students from committing suicide. The most effective prevention programs start with younger students and portray suicide as a mental health problem, not a dramatic way of ending a life. It is essential that counsellors involve the parents of troubled students in the counselling process (Jones, 2001). Baker and Gerler (2014) reported that students who participated in a school counselling program had significantly less inappropriate behaviors and more positive attitudes toward school than those students who did not participate in the program.

5. METHODOLOGY

The research was designed to be descriptive. This is because there is already existing good amount of literature on the impact of guidance and counseling among students and pupils, yet not much was available for Ghana.

5.1 Population and Sampling

The population of the study was all students in the public and private Senior High Schools in Madina-Adenta Municipality of the Greater Accra Region. The total of senior high schools stands at 11 with an estimated total population of 3500 as at 20th June, 2017. Purposive sampling was used to sample the respondents. Form 3 students were selected because have spent almost three years in the school and they might have gone through some form of guidance and counselling at one time in the school. A process of simple random sampling is used to choose 50 Form 3 students from one private school and 50 Form 3 students from a government school. In all a total of 100 sample size was used for the study. The Senior High Schools chosen for the study were West African Senior High School and Action Progressive Institute. Even though West African Senior High School is a government school there was no known teacher or personnel dedicated to guidance and counselling. Action Progressive Institute a private school at Madina Estate has two teachers who apart from teaching also engage in counselling the students on all manner of issues.

5.2 Data collection

Semi-structured questionnaires with both closed and open-ended questions were administered. The questionnaire consisted of two sections, Section A and section B. Section A consisted of items pertaining to profile of the respondents while section B consisted of items pertaining to the area of study. The students' questionnaires to obtain quantitative data was found to be the most appropriate tool since large amount of information would be collected from a sample size of appreciable number within expected period of time. Also the quantitative data could be easily analyzed more scientifically and objectively while the results could easily be quantified by use of software, (Mugenda & Mugenda, 1999). The questionnaire was constructed based on the five Likert scaled with weighted values assigned; thus it provided respondents with a series of statements in which they could indicate the degree of agreement or disagreement, that is: Strongly Agree – 5.00 (SA), Agree-4.00 (A), Indifference- 3.00 (I), Disagree-2.00 (D) or Strongly Disagree-1.00 (SD).

5.3 Data Collection and Analysis

Data collection method adopted is generally primary data collection. This was done by means of the questionnaires. The sets of questionnaires and interview guides were pre-tested on selected respondents to necessitate adjustments in order to make them more suitable and minimize bias in responses. Questionnaires were distributed to the students while they are in the classrooms. Administering the questionnaire classroom was the most convenient approach, because their full attention was received to respond to the questions. This also ensured that the response rate was high for the questionnaires.

The data obtained from the data collection was entered into the software SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences). Some descriptive statistical information was generated on some of the variables/questions being considered. Cross-tabulation was also used to compare between one set of results and another and examine if there is a possible relationship between them. The tables were produced to provide pictorial views of what is being explained or described from the results obtained.

6. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Demographics

Gender of Respondents

Table 6.1: Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Male	42	42
Female	58	58

Source: Research Fieldwork

The results show that more than half of the respondents, 57%, who took part in the study were females and 42% were males. This may be a fair representation of the gender distribution in the two Senior High Schools. It is observed that at about a decade ago, more males than females are able to get to the Senior High level on the educational ladder. However, with government support for Senior High Schools increasing, more intakes are being done and a lot more females are able to get access equally just as their male counterparts. The gender proportion of the students in the senior high schools may improve further with more education in the rural communities who believe girls are made for the kitchen. This result nonetheless is an improvement from yesteryears.

Table 6.2: Age of Respondents

Gender	Minimum	Average	Maximum
Male	15	16.7	18
Female	15	16.2	18

Source: Research Fieldwork

The average age of the most of the Form 3 students surveyed was around 16 years. The average age for the males was 16.7 years while that of the females was 16.2 years. This means that generally while the maximum and minimum ages of both males and females may be the same, with the average age of the males being higher than females indicate that there are older males than females in the schools.

Availability of Guidance and Counselling in the Schools**Does your School offer Guidance and Counselling****Table 6.3: Does school offer Guidance and Counselling**

Does school offer Guidance and Counselling	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Yes	38	38
No	14	14
Don't Know	48	48

Source: Research Fieldwork

Close to half of the students, 48%, do not know at all that there may be guidance and counselling services in their schools which they could access. Nonetheless, there is an encouraging proportion of 38% who are aware of the counselling services in their schools. A further 14% of the respondents stated an outright 'No' to the knowledge of counselling services in the school. For those who mentioned an outright 'No' there seems to be nothing in the school that tells them guidance and counselling services may be available or none of their friends have accessed any of those services. The commonness of the responses of those who said outright 'No' and those who said they 'Don't Know' is that both are not aware of the presence of guidance and counselling in their schools. Clearly, there are some who knew that their school offered guidance and counselling. This is according to 38% of the respondents.

This is an indication that the schools may not be having effective orientation programs for new students or may not be doing orientation at all. This is because if such orientations are done properly the students would know of the presence of such programs and the teachers that have been assigned to handle such programs.

Have you ever gone to your teachers to seek guidance and counselling?**Table 6.4: Have you ever gone to your teachers to seek guidance and counselling**

Have you ever gone to your teachers to seek guidance and counselling	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Yes	15	15
No	85	85

Source: Research Fieldwork

Out of the 38% who know of the guidance and counselling services in the school, an amazing 85% have never gone out to seek guidance and counselling services. Even though 38% of the respondents say they know there is a counsellor in the school, only 15% have accessed such services.

A number of factors may contribute to this apathy. It possible some students after seeking counselling on something sensitive to them, that issue may be been leaked; a situation where the confidentiality and private nature of the counselling session may not have been protected but compromised. In a situation like this, students would not want to avail themselves to counselling at all. Another possible reason to this apathy is that, most students will already not find seeking advice of an adult, especially their teachers, it natural. Typically in the Ghanaian context where children hardly talk to their parents or the elderly about their challenges, this may be expected. But the level of extent of non-patronage is too high.

Table 6.5: Cross tabulation of Gender and Seeking for Guidance and Counselling

Gender	Have you ever sought guidance and counselling from your teachers			
	<i>Yes</i>		<i>No</i>	
	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>Male</i>	31	31.3	69	68.7
<i>Female</i>	69	68.7	31	31.3

Source: Research Fieldwork

The cross tabulation above shows that females seek counselling more than males. Among the few students that had gone to seek guidance and counselling from their teachers, about two-thirds.

Table 6.6: Does the school organize programs that seek to guide and counsel students

Does the school organize programs that seek to guide and counsel students	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Yes	98	98
No	2	2

Source: Research Fieldwork

On the organization of guidance and counselling programs in the schools by staff or external stakeholders, 98% responded they are aware of such programs. This is positive compared to 38% who do not know guidance and counselling services are being done in the school. Nonetheless, it is because such programs are usually announced at school assembly sessions, it is hard to miss knowledge of them.

Table 6.7: Have you participated in a guidance and counselling program organized by your school

Have you participated in a guidance and counselling program organized by your school	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Yes	76	76
No	24	24

Source Research Fieldwork

In spite of 98% knowing about guidance and counselling programs in the schools, a lower proportion of 76% have actually participated in such programs. This means that either such programs are not made compulsory in the students or some of the students just don't participate. In comparing the participation of guidance and counselling programs to that of those who have gone to their teachers to seek personal guidance and counselling sessions, the participation of the former is much better.

The point is that if something cannot be achieved with one-one guidance and counselling, organization of mass programs can be of help. It is possible that the organization of such programs may have also contributed to students not seeking personal one-one counselling from their teachers.

Table 6.8: Have you ever counselling from friends/mates

Have you ever counselling from friends/mates	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Yes	94	94
No	6	6

Source: Research Fieldwork

The results from the table are a direct opposite of the results from Table . This is obviously showing that the students are more comfortable speaking to their peers and so regularly seek counselling from them. Many other researches show that young people seek counselling from their peers more than from professional or institutional designated counselling places.

Most young people trust their mates and colleagues, and moreover those people are handy; they can easily be found to be told worrying issues. It is therefore important that young people begin to be trained as peer counsellors to be able to offer the kind of advice and support some of their colleagues may need. In that case even though most of them do not go to places they are likely to get the best counselling, their peers, whom they can easily access, can be of a good help to them as well.

Table 6.9: Topics Discussed during Guidance and Counselling

Topics Discussed during Guidance and Counselling	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Academics	38	38
Family	17	17
Financial	45	47
Boy Girl Relationship	0	0
Sexual Harassment	0	0

Source: Research Fieldwork

Discussion of financial challenges is one of the top things the SHS students discussed with their teachers during counselling. This is according to 45% of those who responded that they have had counselling sessions with their teachers. The top list is followed by 38% who discussed their academic standings, challenges and performances with teachers for solutions. Family also appeared to be topical in these discussions. Interestingly, none of students, even though few of them had for guidance and counselling, discussed matters of Boy Girl relationship or any form of sexual harassment (which is a topical issue in our society today).

Table 6.10: Matters discussed when guidance and Counselling programs were organized

Matters discussed when guidance and Counselling programs were organized	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Academics	39	39
Family	0	0
Financial	0	0
Boy Girl Relationship	43	43
Sexual Harassment	0	0
Others	18	18

Source: Research Fieldwork

The students mentioned that much of the topics and discussions that sought to give them guidance and counselling were focused on their academics, relating with the opposite sex and other issues. There was no mention of talk or discussion on family and financial matters. Sexual harassment is also not really talked about. Studies by Lapan et al (2003), indicate that some of the top issues that affect the wellbeing of students in school are their academics, sexuality and boy-girl relationships, finances and family problems.

It is positive the students found the guidance and counselling programs speaking to their needs. The one that spoke to their needs loudest is the talk and discussions on boy-girl relationships, according to 43% of the students. This is followed by their academics. It is obvious that the students received more guidance and counselling outside topics related to their academics. On the others, the students mentioned issues of spirituality as the main topics.

Table 6.11: Matters discussed when peer guidance and Counselling was sought

Matters discussed when peer guidance and Counselling was sought	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Academics	24	24
Family	21	21
Financial	19	19
Boy Girl Relationship	32	32
Sexual Harassment	4	4

Source: Research Fieldwork

Comparing the differences and similarities in three counselling contacts above, that is, going personally to teachers, organization of counselling programs and seeking guidance and counselling from friends, friends seems to be the most popular. Students contact their friends and seek guidance and counselling on almost every issue. This confirms the need to promote and encourage peer guidance and counselling training in schools so that students can be able to seek help from qualified colleagues.

Table 6.12: Number of times students sought counselling

Number of times students sought counselling	Min	Average	Max
Can you remember how many times you have sought guidance and counselling from your teachers/school counsellor	1	1.5	2
Can you remember how many times you have sought guidance and counselling from your friends/colleagues	Many times	Many times	Many times

Source: Research Fieldwork

On average, the students have accessed counselling from their school counsellors less than twice. On the other hand most of them responded 'many times', to how many times they have sought guidance and counselling from friends and colleagues.

The impact of Guidance and Counselling

Table 6.13: Has seeking guidance and counselling improved your life in any way

Has seeking guidance and counselling improved your life in any way	Frequency	Percentages (%)
Yes	100	100
No	0	0

Source: Research Fieldwork

There was an overwhelming response from the students that the guidance and counselling they may have obtained, either from their teachers, friends or external resource persons have contributed to an improvement.

The table below looks at the breakdown of the reasons for the improvements, based on the Likert scale responses. The responses were assigned the following weights, Strongly Agree -5.0, Agree - 4.0, Indifferent - 3.0, Disagree - 2.0, Strongly Disagree - 1.0.

Table 6.14: Number of times students sought counselling

Number of times students sought counselling	Min	Average	Max
Academic Success – My academic performance is improving, even though it may not be the best	2	3.6	5
Self-awareness – I am more conscious of my strengths and weaknesses as a person	1	3.7	4
Interpersonal relationships – I relate better with other people even those, I don't like	5	3.8	1

Source: Research Fieldwork

On Academic Success, the highest response received is 5, that is, strongly agree and lowest response received is 2. This means that while some responded that they strongly agree to improvement others do not agree. However, generally, an average response of 3.6, suggests that the general response of the students is more towards agreeing to an improvement in their academic lives as a result of counseling. Similarly, the average response of 3.7 for self-awareness indicates that, most of the students agree they are more conscious of their strengths and weaknesses as people.

On interpersonal relationships, the students had an average response of 3.8. The closeness of the responses to 4.0

Table 6.15: Number of times students sought counselling

Number of times students sought counselling	Min	Average	Max
Academic Success – My academic performance is improving, even though it may not be the best	2	3.9	5
Self-awareness – I am more conscious of my strengths and weaknesses as a person	1	3.6	5

Source: Research Fieldwork

Table 6.16: Number of times students sought counselling

Number of times students sought counselling	Min	Average	Max
Management of fear – I am better able to deal with fear and more confident	1	3.2	4
Dealing with grief – I am better able loss. The loss of a property or a loved one	1	2.6	4

Source: Research Fieldwork

In a similar vein, with mean responses of 3.9 and 3.6, the students are in agreement that they are developing in their social values and also growing in the way they manage anger.

Table 6.17: Number of times students sought counselling

Number of times students sought counselling	Min	Average	Max
Management of fear – I am better able to deal with fear and more confident	1	3.2	4
Dealing with grief – I am better able loss. The loss of a property or a loved one	1	2.6	4

Source: Research Fieldwork

For management of fear, the average response of 3.2 is more of indifferent. This means that generally, most of the students have not developed better confidence and ability to deal with fear. And finally on dealing with grief, the mean response of 2.6, clearly shows that the students have not developed in dealing with grief. This may apparently be because they not have had grieving experiences so would not be able to better assess that situation in their lives.

It is important to note that even though there was no response from the students that guidance and counselling has not made any improvement in their lives, for the various topical sections above, quite a number responded 'Disagree' and 'Strongly Disagree'. This indicates that some students have not seen improvement in their lives with regards to the sections but definitely there have been an improvement in their lives, at least with regards to one of the topical sections above.

7. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

More students are noted not to have gone for one-on-one guidance and counselling. As noted in the results and analysis above, some factors may contribute to this. However, if much effort is put in to ensure that confidentiality of the students are protected it would begin to yield a lot more positive results. It became clear that females sought counselling more than the male students. Specifically, a third of males sought counselling while two-thirds of females do. The students do not usually seek counselling from their teachers or dedicated staff that trained to do counselling but relied more on their peers.

8. CONCLUSION

It can be assessed that guidance and counselling is pervasive in the schools that were considered for the study. However, the pervasiveness of the counselling was less about personal one-on-one counselling. It was more on the basis of giving general advice to students through the organization of relevant programs. While this approach may be noted to make some

impact, it is also widely noted that one-on-one guidance and counselling that sought to specifically help an individual goes much further to impact in the lives of the persons involved.

The results from the study indicate that counselling does have effect on the students. Assessing the impact of the guidance and counselling, the students indicates that those guidance and counselling sessions, no matter the form they took, made positive impacts and improvement in their lives.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

It is recommended that students are trained as peer counselling. More peer counselling programs in SHS schools would improve students' lives and may results series of bad decisions being taken by the students. A lot more effort should be put in by school authorities in second cycle institutions to make guidance and counselling popular and accepted concept among the students.

It is recommended that a more comprehensive study is conducted of SHS students around the country to ascertain the true state of guidance and counselling in the second cycle schools. Further assessment of the role of counselling in the schools can be done where suggestion for improvements can be instituted. This can guide GES and the government of Ghana in coming out with policies that will help share the lives and future of those students while they are their formative years.

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